

1 Active animal health surveillance in European Union Member 2 States: Gaps and opportunities

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31 *SUMMARY*

32 Animal health surveillance enables the detection and control of animal diseases including zoonoses.
33 Under the EU-FP7 project RISKSUR, a survey was conducted in 11 EU Member States and Switzerland
34 to describe active surveillance components in 2011 managed by the public or private sector and
35 identify gaps and opportunities. Information was collected about the hazard, target population,
36 geographical focus, legal obligation, management, surveillance design, risk-based sampling, and
37 multi-hazard surveillance. Two countries were excluded due to incompleteness of data. Most of the
38 664 components targeted cattle (26.7%), pigs (17.5%) or poultry (16.0%). The most common
39 surveillance objectives were demonstrating freedom from disease (43.8%) and case detection
40 (26.8%). Over half of components applied risk-based sampling (57.1%), but mainly focused on a
41 single population stratum (targeted risk-based) rather than differentiating between risk levels of
42 different strata (stratified risk-based). About a third of components were multi-hazard (37.3%). Both
43 risk-based sampling and multi-hazard surveillance were used more frequently in privately funded
44 components. The study identified several gaps (e.g. lack of systematic documentation, inconsistent
45 application of terminology) and opportunities (e.g. stratified risk-based sampling). The greater
46 flexibility provided by the new EU Animal Health Law means that systematic evaluation of
47 surveillance alternatives will be required to optimize cost-effectiveness.

48 INTRODUCTION

49 Animal health surveillance (AHS) forms a key element in the detection and control of animal and
50 zoonotic diseases, in demonstrating disease freedom to ensure safe trade and providing valuable
51 data for decision-support [1]. A key feature of surveillance is the need for the systematic (continuous
52 or repeated) measurement, collection, collation, analysis, interpretation, and timely dissemination of
53 data [2]. Hence, single surveys or analytical studies do not fall under this surveillance definition. The
54 need for systematic analysis and interpretation arises from the close link between surveillance and
55 intervention strategies in case undesired changes are observed [3], which distinguishes surveillance
56 from monitoring systems. Monitoring, i.e. the collection of animal health data without a clear related
57 action plan, usually only applies when the aim is to assess the initial health status of a population,
58 whilst otherwise data collection without a clear related action plan should not be encouraged [4]. In
59 contrast to passive surveillance, which relies on the detection and reporting of clinical signs, active
60 surveillance is initiated by the investigator using a defined protocol to perform actions that are
61 scheduled in advance [2]. Whilst public health surveillance commonly relies on notifiable disease
62 reporting (passive surveillance) and the analysis of secondary data, AHS places stronger emphasis on
63 collecting primary data via active surveillance for example to fulfill trade requirements and ensure
64 food safety.

65 In the European Union (EU) AHS is regulated by the Community Animal Health Policy (CAHP), which
66 aims to reduce the negative impact of animal diseases on animal and public health, animal welfare,
67 and the economy by ensuring safe intra-community trade with live animals and animal products [5].
68 Historically, the CAHP included almost 50 basic directives and regulations and 400 pieces of
69 secondary legislation, most of which were adopted between 1988 and 1995 [1]. An external
70 evaluation launched by the Commission in 2004 to assess the performance of the CAHP concluded
71 that it lacks an overall strategy, places insufficient focus on disease prevention and does not provide
72 enough flexibility to adapt new scientific and technological developments. Audit reports also

73 indicated different interpretations of requirements e.g. regarding specifications of risk categories as
74 part of the multi-annual national control plan, resulting in diverse surveillance approaches taken by
75 Member States [6]. The new EU Animal Health Law published in March 2016 [7] is based on the EU
76 Animal Health Strategy “Prevention is better than cure” [5] and streamlines the huge number of legal
77 acts into a single law, which shall also prevent piecemeal and crisis-driven policy development in the
78 future [1]. Besides EU regulations, national and regional requirements as well as private initiatives
79 exist, which vary between countries. Hence, the surveillance landscape in the EU includes a mixture
80 of regulated and non-regulated activities managed by the public sector, private sector or both.

81 Given budget limitations, it is crucial to carefully design and regularly evaluate surveillance systems
82 to optimize cost-effectiveness. Traditionally, input-based standards were applied, which required
83 specific activities to be carried out regardless of the characteristics of the population. In recent years,
84 considerable progress has been made regarding surveillance design. Alternative approaches include
85 the application of output-based standards [8, 9], where surveillance is designed to meet defined
86 requirements (surveillance sensitivity, design prevalence), thus supporting flexible approaches
87 targeted to the characteristics of the population under surveillance and the available capacities. Two
88 probabilistic output-based measures are applied, i.e. the probability (“confidence”) of detecting a
89 case (surveillance sensitivity) and the probability that a population is free from disease (negative
90 predictive value) [8]. Whilst surveillance sensitivity allows achieving the targeted probability at the
91 set design prevalence for different testing regimes, sample sizes and risk strata, the negative
92 predictive value provides opportunities to combine information from multiple surveillance
93 components and to take the value of historical information into account [8, 10, 11]. Consequently,
94 heterogeneity in populations can be more adequately accounted for including various risk levels [9],
95 and surveillance effectiveness can be quantified in populations that are too small to achieve the
96 desired probability of detection by applying input-based standards [10-12]. Hence, these probabilistic
97 approaches offer opportunities to lower costs whilst achieving the same target or achieve greater
98 effectiveness at the same cost. Various analyses have been published demonstrating the superiority

99 of output-based over input-based standards or risk-based over random sampling strategies. For
100 instance, it was estimated that risk-based strategies reduced the cost to demonstrate freedom from
101 infectious bovine rhinotracheitis and enzootic bovine leucosis in the EU between 2002 and 2009 by
102 six million Euros [13]. Output-based standards have been evaluated for example for *Trichinella* spp.
103 [14], Bovine Herpes virus 1 [15], Avian Influenza virus [16], Transmissible Spongiform
104 Encephalopathies [17, 18], *Mycobacterium bovis subsp. tuberculosis* [19-22], *Mycobacterium avium*
105 *subsp. paratuberculosis* [11, 23, 24], Classical Swine Fever virus [25], Bluetongue Disease virus [26],
106 and resistant pathogens [27]. However, output-based approaches need to be based on sound
107 epidemiological knowledge including an evaluation of the epidemiological situation in the region,
108 require close collaboration and exchange between scientists and policy makers [13] and need to be
109 documented in a transparent manner to allow cross-country comparisons [28].

110 For early detection (or early-warning surveillance), alternative approaches include for example
111 sentinel, participatory and syndromic surveillance strategies [29]. Syndromic surveillance can be
112 defined as “surveillance of health indicators and diseases in defined populations in order to increase
113 the likelihood of timely detection of undefined (new) or unexpected (exotic or re-emerging) threats”
114 [2]. By detecting a disease early, potential devastating consequences of spread and thus economic
115 impacts can be considerably minimised [28, 30]. Testing the same samples simultaneously for
116 multiple hazards (multi-hazard surveillance) presents a general option to reduce surveillance costs
117 and thus provides an important alternative to consider compared to targeting a single hazard only.

118 Although these approaches are increasingly promoted in scientific research, there is a lack of
119 overview of AHS activities in EU countries and to what extent alternative strategies are already in
120 place. Therefore, as part of the EU-FP7 RISKSUR project (2012-2015) (<http://www.fp7-risksur.eu/>), a
121 survey was carried out to describe existing surveillance activities in EU countries, with the aim to
122 identify gaps and opportunities. Furthermore, a better understanding of existing surveillance

123 activities and differences between countries also contributed to inform the development of decision
124 support tools for the design and evaluation of surveillance systems (<http://webtools.fp7-risksur.eu/>).

125 **METHODS**

126 *Survey design:* The reference year was 2011 as this was the latest reporting period for which
127 expenditures were accessible at the time of data collection (spring to autumn 2013). All seven
128 “partner countries” (CH, DE, ES, FR, NL, SE, UK) of the RISKSUR consortium as well as five selected
129 “non-partner countries” (BG, CZ, DK, IE, IT) were included in the data collection process
130 (subsequently referred to as study countries). Non-partner countries had been selected based on
131 dissimilarity to partner countries regarding geographical region (e.g. targeting countries from Eastern
132 and Southern Europe) and animal populations, production systems and hazards present, as well as
133 the availability of a responsive official contact person. Furthermore, an in-country contact person
134 had to be available to support data collection, especially due to language barriers and insufficient
135 publicly accessible information on surveillance components, which would not have allowed for data
136 collection otherwise.

137 Sequential numbers were randomly assigned to countries to preserve confidentiality. All hazards
138 (e.g. pathogens, syndromes, antimicrobial resistance, animal welfare) and species were covered,
139 regardless of whether surveillance was managed by the public or private sector. Surveillance
140 associated with import or export testing was not considered as requirements depend on the trading
141 partners of the respective country. Even though data were collected on active and passive
142 components, only active surveillance components were considered in this analysis as data on passive
143 surveillance were considered to be too similar between countries.

144 *Questionnaire design:* A questionnaire, comprising two sections with a total of 26 variables, was
145 designed to collect information on surveillance components (see Supplementary Section S1 for a
146 copy of the questionnaire and Supplementary Table S1 for examples). A surveillance component was

147 defined as a single surveillance activity used to investigate the occurrence of one or more hazards or
148 health events in a specified population, and which has a self-contained (i.e. conclusive and
149 comprehensive in itself) surveillance protocol that focusses on a particular data source. The
150 following key variables were used for analysis: targeted threat, disease or health event, target
151 population, species and sector(s), geographical focus (local, national or regional), primary purpose,
152 legal obligation, management (private, public or both), description of the component, study design
153 (e.g. survey, continuous data collection), case definition (e.g. laboratory test for pathogen/toxins or
154 host response, clinical signs, pathology, indirect indicators), risk-based sampling, and multi-hazard
155 surveillance. Cost information is not presented in this paper as data gaps were too large to make
156 meaningful inferences. Risk-based sampling was defined as “preferentially sampling strata within the
157 target population that are more likely to be exposed, affected, detected, become affected, transmit
158 infection, or cause other consequences” [4]. For risk-based components, a post-hoc distinction was
159 further made between targeted risk-based (focusing only on one sub-stratum of the population) and
160 stratified risk-based (sampling intensity differs between population strata). Multi-hazard surveillance
161 was defined as “surveillance activities where samples collected for one disease agent are analysed
162 for more than one purpose or for other disease agents, either in parallel or at a later stage”. For the
163 surveillance definitions and characteristics used in the questionnaire, data collectors were referred
164 to the final report from the International Conference on Animal Health Surveillance (ICAHS) in May
165 2011 [4].

166 *Data collection:* The questionnaire was circulated within the RISKSUR consortium to collate feedback.
167 Twenty-nine staff from RISKSUR partner countries collected the data in their own country and in
168 collaboration with the assigned contact person in non-partner countries. All but one data collector
169 were either trained veterinarians (n = 24) or animal scientists (n = 5). One external data collector who
170 was temporarily employed in one non-partner country to ensure that language did not present a
171 barrier was not working in the veterinary field. A training session was held with data collectors via
172 Skype to review the protocol and thus standardize data collection. After approval by the RVC ethics

173 committee (No. 2013 0071H: Ethical clearance for RISKSUR mapping), a database was developed in
174 Microsoft ACCESS® (Microsoft Corporation, Redmond, Virginia) and distributed amongst data
175 collectors. Information on surveillance components was predominantly collected through a grey
176 literature search, including government or non-government reports, national legislations and other
177 information, whilst scientific literature only sometimes provided indications of surveillance efforts.
178 Representatives from public and private institutions were contacted to verify or complement
179 information [31]. Finally, data were re-entered into a shared web-based SQL database.

180 *Data management:* Seven researchers from six institutes (APHA, CIRAD, FLI, RVC, SVA, UCM) spent
181 two months on consistency checks of a sub-set of the database [31], which included discussions on
182 standardized use of terminology and application to recorded components. A terminology working
183 group was initiated to verify conclusions regarding means of data acquisition and surveillance
184 purpose and objective [32]. Based on the results of this working group, the term 'surveillance
185 objective' will be used instead of 'surveillance purpose' throughout the text. Prior to preparing this
186 manuscript, a final consistency check was performed by a single investigator. This involved checking
187 categorisations once again of those key variables, for which strong inconsistencies were identified
188 during the initial consistency checks (i.e. surveillance objective, means of data acquisition, and risk-
189 based sampling) and verification that components were consistently split according to the following
190 criteria: 1) Individual hazard(s) unless for unspecific components (e.g. meat inspection); 2) specified
191 population: Species and if applicable target sector; 3) data source: Sampling point, case definition; 4)
192 risk-based sampling; and 5) data collection method (means of data acquisition, study design).

193 *Data analysis:* Data were analysed in Stata (StataCorp. 2015. *Stata Statistical Software: Release 14*.
194 College Station, TX: StataCorp LP). A stacked bar chart of the number of components stratified by the
195 sector managing the component (public, private, both, unknown) was created. Countries with
196 obvious deficiencies in data completeness were excluded from subsequent analyses. Surveillance
197 component was chosen as the level of analysis. The percentage and 95% confidence interval of

198 components (number of recorded components / total number of recorded components) were
199 calculated for each variable using the *cii command*. Associations between each variable with the
200 independent variables management, species and objective were explored using r x c contingency
201 tables. Cells with low frequencies were collapsed or discarded if considered appropriate. The
202 conditional probabilities (column percentages; *tabulate command*) and adjusted residuals (*tabchi*
203 *command*) were reported. Any cell with adjusted residuals greater than ± 1.96 was highlighted in
204 bold, as they are more extreme than would be expected if the null hypothesis of independence was
205 true [33].

206 Completeness of surveillance components per country was estimated by matching the components
207 recorded by each country with all obligatory EU components identified in the dataset (see
208 Supplementary Table S2) and dividing the achieved number by the total. An EU component was
209 considered obligatory if it was compulsory for any EU Member State, not just relating to restriction
210 zones or countries with eradication programmes in place.

211 **RESULTS**

212 *Descriptive results*

213 The dataset prior to the final consistency check included 738 active AHS components. Seventy-three
214 components were excluded as they were combined with another component ($n = 42$), failed to meet
215 the surveillance definition ($n = 10$), included insufficient information ($n = 8$), related to export/import
216 ($n = 8$), or were duplicates or considered erroneous ($n = 5$). Twenty-two components were added as
217 recorded variables justified splitting the original component to achieve consistency in component
218 splitting with other countries. Hence, the final dataset included 687 components.

219 The number of active AHS components recorded per country (median: 57.5; range: 10 – 105)
220 stratified by the sector responsible for management (public, private or both) is shown in
221 Supplementary Figure S1. In most countries, components were predominantly managed publicly

222 (median across countries: 65.6%; IQR: 47.5 – 75.7%) with a smaller percentage being managed
223 privately (median: 19.8%; IQR: 9.3 – 25.6%) or in a public-private partnership (median: 7.9%; IQR: 3.9
224 – 10.8%).

225 Countries 5 (n = 13) and 11 (n = 10) were excluded from subsequent analyses as their data were
226 considered to be too incomplete, thus resulting in 664 components in the final data set. The
227 remaining countries reported 34.1 to 90.2% of the 43 obligatory EU components identified in the
228 data set (median: 59.8%; interquartile range: 48.2 – 84.1%) (see Supplementary Table S2).

229 Components targeted 55 specific hazards (592 components), 21 hazard groups (e.g. wildlife diseases,
230 emerging diseases) (n = 62) and three indicators (genetic, health, welfare) (n = 10). Supplementary
231 Table S3 shows the number of components per hazard, the number of countries reporting at least
232 one component for this hazard, and the median, minimum and maximum number of components for
233 those latter countries. The most frequent hazards targeted by the hazard-specific components were
234 *Salmonella* spp. (16.1%), *Brucella* spp. (7.7%), *Mycobacterium tuberculosis* (4.4%), Classical Swine
235 Fever virus (3.9%), bluetongue disease virus (3.8%), avian influenza virus, scrapie virus and *Trichinella*
236 spp. (3.6% each), and Aujeszky's disease and Enzootic Bovine Leucosis (3.3% each).

237 Descriptive results for all study countries and stratified by partner and non-partner countries are
238 presented in Table 1. Categories of three variables significantly differed between partner and non-
239 partner countries, i.e. legal requirement, management and risk-based sampling.

240 Cattle were the most frequent species targeted by components (26.7%), followed by pigs (17.5%),
241 poultry (16.0%), and small ruminants (11.9%). Country 9 did not record any wildlife components and
242 countries 1 and 7 only one general wildlife component. The category 'other species' covered fish (13
243 components), insect vectors (n = 9), and bees (n = 3). Less than five components were recorded for
244 molluscs, shellfish or crustaceans (n = 4), animal feed (n = 4), and pets (n = 1). Most components
245 were implemented at the national level (89.4%) and were based on EU regulations (68.4%). Twelve
246 percent of components were based on additional national requirements.

247 The most commonly assigned surveillance objective was demonstrating freedom from disease
248 (43.8%), followed by case detection (26.8%), prevalence estimation (19.7%), and early detection
249 (9.8%). The sampling point was recorded as farm, abattoir, and insemination centre for 48.6%,
250 21.4%, and 15.6% of components, respectively. Data were usually recorded to be collected
251 continuously (56.8%) or via repeated (usually annual) surveys (39.2%). Case reports (n = 15), sentinel
252 surveillance (n = 8), participatory surveillance (n = 2), and event-based surveillance (n = 1) were
253 recorded under 'other study designs'. Laboratory diagnosis (direct, indirect or both) was the most
254 common case definition. Active clinical surveillance (n = 12), i.e. routine inspection by the competent
255 authority without prior notification of abnormal signs by farmers, targeted Bluetongue disease,
256 Classical Swine Fever and emerging diseases in more than one country. Most 'other case definitions'
257 contained multiple case definitions including others than laboratory detection (e.g. indirect
258 indicators, risk factors). Risk-based sampling and multi-hazard surveillance were recorded for 57.1%
259 and 37.3% of components, respectively.

260 *Bivariate results: Management*

261 Components managed in a public-private partnership were more likely recorded (than what would
262 be expected if the variables were independent) by partner (85.3%) than non-partner countries
263 (14.8%) (Table 2). Privately managed components more frequently targeted cattle (46.6%) and less
264 frequently small ruminants (8.4%) than public components (34.0% and 21.5%, respectively). Sixty
265 percent of private components compared to 39.9% of public components aimed to demonstrate
266 freedom from disease. In contrast, prevalence estimation and early detection were more frequently
267 recorded as surveillance objective for public (22.7% and 11.5%) than for private components (8.6%
268 and 3.3%). Continuous data collection was more commonly managed publicly (61.2%) than privately
269 (39.5%), whilst repeated surveys were more predominant for private (58.6%) than public
270 components. Risk-based strategies and multi-hazard surveillance were more often recorded for
271 privately (66.0% and 68.1%, respectively) than for publicly managed components (53.1% and 28.6%,
272 respectively).

273 *Bivariate results: Species*

274 Components targeting pigs were more likely based on additional national regulations (23.0%) than
275 those targeting poultry (6.1%) (Table 3). The objective of demonstrating freedom from disease was
276 more likely recorded for cattle and pigs (59.1% and 58.6%) than for poultry (15.1%). Case detection
277 was more frequently recorded for poultry (65.1%) compared to the other three species groups,
278 whilst prevalence estimation was more likely recorded for small ruminants (35.4%) compared to
279 poultry (8.5%). Farm was more frequently recorded as sampling point for poultry and small
280 ruminants (61.3 – 89.1%) than for cattle (46.0%) and pigs (37.2%), whilst abattoir was more common
281 for surveillance components targeting pigs (38.1%) compared to poultry (10.9%). Risk-based
282 strategies were relatively seldom recorded for pigs (50.4%), whilst multi-hazard surveillance was
283 relatively frequent for pigs (59.0%) and cattle (44.0%). In contrast, multi-hazard surveillance was
284 relatively uncommon for poultry (8.1%).

285 *Bivariate results: Surveillance objective*

286 The objective prevalence estimation was more frequently recorded by partner (72.9%) than by non-
287 partner countries (27.1%) (Table 4). Components were more commonly implemented at the national
288 level for the objective of demonstrating disease freedom than for early detection and at the regional
289 level vice versa. Seventy-six percent of components with the objective of demonstrating freedom
290 from disease were regulated by the EU compared to 45.5% of components aimed at early detection.
291 Components aimed at early detection were more frequently regulated by national regulations or
292 voluntary programmes than components with other objectives. At the farm level, the most frequent
293 objectives were case detection (79.4%) and early detection (71.7%). The objective of annual surveys
294 at insemination centres was consistently categorized as demonstrating freedom from disease
295 (100%). Components aimed at demonstrating freedom from disease most commonly applied risk-
296 based sampling (63.3%) and multi-hazard surveillance (59.5%) compared to other objectives (44.2 –
297 57.9% and 12.8 – 35.1%, respectively).

298 *Risk-based sampling*

299 The most frequent risk factors were production type (breeder, grower), age, region, herd size, and
300 time period (Table 5). Of these top five risk factors, production type, age, and herd size
301 predominantly included targeted risk-based strategies, where only a single stratum is under
302 surveillance (e.g. only breeders or only animals above a certain age). In contrast, for the risk factor
303 region, the component description mostly indicated stratified risk-based sampling, e.g. targeting
304 regions with different sampling intensity depending on differences in epidemiological situation or risk
305 of introduction. For the risk factor period, both targeted (e.g. sampling at the end of high risk period
306 to demonstrate freedom from disease) and stratified risk-based approaches (varying sampling
307 intensities between seasons) were reported.

308 **DISCUSSION**

309 To the authors' knowledge, this is the first systematic analysis of publicly and privately funded AHS
310 components in EU Member States and Switzerland. Generating an overview of all active AHS
311 components covering the public and private sectors and the full range of hazards and species was
312 challenging as existence and design of surveillance components are generally not systematically
313 documented [31]. Hence, gaps and opportunities were identified not just related to AHS design, but
314 also to the ease and quality of data collection. This survey showed that the public and private sectors
315 applied a range of activities at the national and regional level in addition to obligatory EU
316 requirements. Even though data quality did not allow any in-depth between-country comparisons,
317 observed patterns across the whole dataset are considered to provide valuable insights into how AHS
318 was performed in 2011 in the ten study countries included in the analysis.

319 *Differences between partner and non-partner countries*

320 Systematic differences may exist between partner and non-partner countries due to the following
321 reasons: Partner countries were comprised only of EU-12 Member States predominantly situated in

322 Central and Western Europe, who have a strong interest in animal health surveillance, which led to
323 their participation in the RISKSUR project. This selection bias was aimed to be reduced by also
324 incorporating EU-15 (CZ) and EU-25 (BG) Member States in the group of non-partner countries,
325 which however also included three EU-12 Member States (DK, IE, IT) thus comprising a more
326 heterogeneous group of Central, Southern and South-Eastern European countries. Furthermore,
327 potential differences in the efforts of collecting the data, data accessibility and availability of contacts
328 may have occurred given that partner countries may have had better contacts to relevant institutions
329 and a stronger interest in data collection given their participation in the project consortium.
330 Acknowledging these potential differences between partner and non-partner countries, we stratified
331 descriptive results and tested for the effect of partner country (yes/no) as part of the bivariate
332 analyses.

333 Descriptive results indicated significant differences between partner and non-partner countries for
334 the variables management (category “both”), legal obligation (EU, private and none) and risk-based
335 sampling (yes/no). The differences in management and legal obligation may indicate stronger
336 investment of partner countries in non-EU regulated privately managed surveillance activities
337 compared to non-partner countries. Another explanation may be that private and voluntary
338 components were better captured in partner than non-partner countries given that data collection
339 was highly challenging, so that a variety of information sources had to be screened and over 20
340 contacts were approached in some countries as part of data collection [34]. The difference in the
341 percentage of risk-based components was not as pronounced as for the variables legal obligation and
342 management. Avian influenza virus and Aujeszky’s disease virus were the only hazards for which the
343 number of total components justified a comparison at the hazard level between partner and non-
344 partner countries. For avian influenza, the difference was driven by one non-partner country
345 recording eight surveillance components, all of which were risk-based as opposed to one to four
346 components recorded by other countries, some of which were risk-based, whilst others were not. For
347 Aujeszky’s disease, wildlife components were only recorded in partner countries ($n = 2$), none of

348 which were risk-based, and abattoir surveillance was recorded as risk-based in both non-partner
349 countries but only in one out of four partner countries recording this component. Therefore, we
350 conclude that the difference can be considered as spurious given that the percentages are to some
351 degree affected by the number of recorded components.

352 Bivariate results indicated a significant effect of partner versus non-partner countries for the
353 variables management (category “both”) and objective (category “prevalence estimation”), but not
354 for the four compared livestock species groups. For the variable management, the same arguments
355 apply as discussed above. The higher number of components aimed at prevalence estimation may
356 indicate that partner countries invest relatively more to assess changes in the hazard situation (e.g.
357 antimicrobial resistance).

358 *Surveillance objective and means of data collection*

359 For active surveillance components, demonstrating freedom from disease was the most common
360 objective, whilst early detection was least common. These objectives are in fact closely linked as
361 activities to demonstrate freedom from disease are generally based on annual surveys, after which
362 early detection is needed to maintain confidence in freedom until the next survey. Early detection
363 activities were underrepresented in the data as passive surveillance components were excluded a
364 priori given that they were considered too similar between countries. However, for many hazards
365 passive surveillance is the predominant early detection component as it is continuously performed
366 on a daily basis across the entire domestic (and wildlife) animal population. Furthermore, it can be
367 highly cost-effective as testing is only performed if disease is suspected. For example Welby *et al* [35]
368 estimated detection probability (component sensitivity; CSe) and cost-effectiveness (CSe/cost in
369 €1000) for three surveillance components targeting Bluetongue virus serotype 8 in Belgium and The
370 Netherlands. Based on a within-herd prevalence of 20% and the assumption that disease awareness
371 is high, passive surveillance resulted in the highest probability of detection (CSe = 0.99) as compared
372 to active cross-sectional surveys (CSe: 0.73 - 0.75) and sentinel surveillance (CSe: 0.29 – 0.33) and a

373 cost efficiency ratio of 1.38 as compared to 0.52 (survey) and 0.41 (sentinel). However, sensitivity of
374 passive surveillance is influenced by the clinical effects of disease, rate of transmission, population
375 structure (e.g. herd size, production system), disease awareness of animal owners and veterinarians,
376 and their preparedness to report [35, 36]. Therefore, it is important to also evaluate the sensitivity of
377 passive surveillance [36], compare strategies to enhance disease awareness (e.g. awareness
378 campaigns, training, adequacy of compensation) and reporting, and assess the acceptability by key
379 stakeholders [37-39]. Effective dissemination of surveillance results to farmers and the public can
380 also enhance engagement of these stakeholders and improve participation.

381 Given these limitations, active surveillance and syndromic surveillance may effectively enhance early
382 detection [29]. Syndromic surveillance is also a (near) real-time surveillance activity aimed at early
383 detection. Compared to passive surveillance, syndromic surveillance is less observer-dependent
384 (depending on data source) and may detect abnormalities (e.g. in animal performance) before
385 clinical signs occur, thus potentially resulting in enhanced timeliness. As part of One Health,
386 syndromic surveillance in animal populations also provides opportunities for the early detection of
387 public health risks [40]. Welby *et al* [35] estimated the probability of syndromic surveillance to detect
388 Bluetongue serotype 8 in NL as 0.98 and 0.99 for milk production data assuming a within-herd
389 prevalence of 2% and 20%, respectively. Despite the high effectiveness that can be achieved via
390 syndromic surveillance, its application requires access to data sources that are sensitive to changes in
391 the level of disease in the population [40] and efficient algorithms that can detect potential outbreak
392 signals [41]. The current study identified 19 syndromic surveillance components recorded by four of
393 the ten study countries. Ten of these components targeted multiple diseases, e.g. emerging diseases
394 (n = 9) or many diseases (n = 1), whereas the remaining components were hazard-specific (n = 5) or
395 targeted disease syndromes, i.e. mastitis or metabolic disorders (n = 4). Diagnostic material and
396 pathology examinations were mentioned as predominant data sources (n = 9). Furthermore,
397 production data (n = 5), information from practitioners (n = 1) and information sources of
398 government, public and charity organizations (n = 1) were recorded, whilst the remaining three

399 components included insufficient information on the data source. These data suggest that
400 syndromic surveillance is not being fully utilised by all countries yet, which is also in line with Dorea
401 *et al* [31].

402 *Risk-based sampling and multi-hazard surveillance*

403 For active components aimed at early detection, comprehensive coverage is generally not cost-
404 effective as disease needs to be detected at very low prevalence to fulfil the aim of early detection
405 [42]. Therefore, risk-based and alternative approaches (e.g. syndromic surveillance) are important to
406 consider to enhance the likelihood of (early) detection. Efforts to demonstrate freedom from disease
407 and detect cases also benefit from risk-based approaches, especially risk-based sampling and risk-
408 based requirement (i.e. incorporation of historical data) [10, 43], as the aim is to detect disease
409 rather than providing representative estimates such as for prevalence estimation. The current data
410 indicate that 50%, 63%, and 57.9% of components with the objectives early detection, demonstrating
411 freedom from disease, and case detection, respectively, included risk-based approaches. Risk-based
412 strategies and multi-hazard surveillance were more commonly recorded for the private sector
413 compared to the public sector. Since 2/3 of private components were based on EU-regulations, this
414 may only be partly explained by less stringent legal requirements. Differences between countries in
415 the extent components are managed publicly or privately may contribute to the higher likelihood of
416 risk-based approaches in the private sector with some countries being more progressive than others.
417 But the private sector may also be under higher pressure to demonstrate cost-effectiveness, which is
418 supported by the fact that the private sector more commonly focussed on aspects with higher
419 economic importance (e.g. cattle and pigs, demonstrating disease freedom to ensure trade). Based
420 on these findings it is hypothesized that risk-based sampling and multi-hazard surveillance could be
421 incorporated more strongly as part of public animal health surveillance.

422 Albeit risk-based sampling was recorded for more than half of components, most of these risk-based
423 components were targeted, only focussing on one population stratum instead of adjusting

424 surveillance intensity according to the risk level of different strata. Whilst it may be justified in some
425 cases to only focus on a single stratum (e.g. serological surveillance in older animals), no statement
426 can be made on the population strata not included. Therefore targeted risk-based sampling as
427 recorded for most of the risk-based components is in fact similar to conventional designs, just being
428 focussed on a single population stratum. Stratified risk-based sampling in contrast distinguishes
429 between high- and low-risk strata of the population. Since all animals have a nonzero probability of
430 being selected, probabilistic statements can still be made for the entire population, but surveillance
431 sensitivity can be increased given a constant sample size or sample size can be reduced at constant
432 target sensitivity. Furthermore, stratified risk-based sampling allows maintaining low level
433 surveillance in low-risk strata to help retain awareness and provide incentives to comply with
434 regulations, e.g. the withdrawal period for antibiotics [27].

435 Movement data provide opportunities to distinguish between farms having a high risk of
436 introduction or spread based on the frequency of in- and out-degree movements and the number
437 and characteristics of trading partners. However, animal movements were only recorded as a risk
438 criterion by two countries (four components), one of which only targeted high turnover premises (i.e.
439 targeted risk-based). Hence, opportunities exist to enhance utilization of quantitative (e.g.
440 movement data), but also qualitative data (e.g. biosecurity level) to distinguish between risk levels of
441 different population strata. The data provided little evidence of the application of alternative
442 approaches such as participatory [44] or event-based surveillance [45].

443 *Legal requirements*

444 Many EU and national legislations still prescribe what has to be done (input-based) rather than what
445 has to be achieved (output-based) and generally focus on a single pathogen. Such input-based
446 requirements do not provide much stimulus to evaluate alternative surveillance designs in order to
447 identify the most cost-effective approach for the specific population to be targeted. Even though
448 input-based standards are simple to compare between countries, they may result in low sensitivity in

449 some population strata and excessive sample numbers in others [9]. EU countries vary considerably
450 in their population structure, trading patterns, hazard situation, and risk factors. Output-based
451 standards allow tailoring surveillance to the population of interest. However, epidemiologically
452 sound application of output-based standards requires epidemiological expertise, knowledge
453 regarding the target population, good data quality, and transparency. Interestingly, more recent
454 regulations (e.g. 2006/88/EC for aquatic animals, 2007/268/EC for avian influenza virus, 1266/2007
455 for bluetongue disease virus – see Supplementary Table S2) encourage application of risk-based
456 approaches and multi-hazard surveillance, indicating that the propagation of these alternative
457 strategies in literature has informed legal requirements. Also, the new EU Animal Health Law
458 explicitly emphasizes the need to take into account the epidemiology of disease, risk factors and
459 characteristics of the target population (Article 27) and allows application of alternative strategies
460 such as accounting for historical data to maintain disease free status (Article 36(1d)). Hence, the new
461 EU Animal Health Law provides enhanced opportunities to apply alternative surveillance approaches
462 to increase effectiveness and cost-efficiency of surveillance.

463 *Importance of hazards*

464 Economic importance and zoonotic potential (7/10 of the most frequent hazards have zoonotic
465 potential) appear to be important drivers for surveillance. As a result, species with little economic
466 value such as pets and wildlife were less frequently covered, which presents another gap in
467 surveillance. For zoonotic diseases, many alternative approaches have been promoted under the
468 concept of One Health including systems thinking, participatory approaches and priority setting [46-
469 49], which can only be achieved via effective collaboration between sectors (public-private) and
470 disciplines (animal-public health). Transparent documentation of surveillance components and
471 formal assessments of the entire surveillance system for a given hazard may also provide
472 opportunities to inform or benefit from these approaches and thus possibly enhance convergence
473 between human and veterinary health agencies. Such One Health approaches are increasingly

474 promoted and present true opportunities to advance the effectiveness of zoonotic disease
475 surveillance, early preparedness and protection of human and animal health in the EU.

476 *Sources of bias*

477 Selection bias might have occurred by including all partner countries and selecting five non-partner
478 countries. However, a systematic and transparent selection process with clearly specified criteria was
479 applied in an effort to minimize selection bias. Due to time and resource constraints, data collection
480 could not be expanded to all EU Member States.

481 Furthermore, information bias may have occurred due to differences between countries in the
482 availability of information and efforts made to seek additional information, centralisation of efforts,
483 and willingness of contacts to share information. The efforts required collecting information on
484 existing public and private surveillance activities covering all hazards and animal species exceeded
485 expectations by far. Therefore, various grey literature sources had to be screened and contact
486 persons approached to gather information on the full range of activities. Many countries have no
487 centralised system capturing at least the existence and design of surveillance system activities.

488 Furthermore, surveillance documentation was more difficult to obtain for the private than the public
489 sector. In a post-hoc questionnaire, data collectors ranked statements that a) the existence and b)
490 the design of surveillance was adequately documented in their country, resulting in a median rank of
491 4 and 3 out of 5 (range 2-5) for public and 2 for both out of 5 (range 1-4) for private components
492 [34]. Data collection also indicated considerable differences between countries regarding evaluation
493 and dissemination of surveillance efforts as well as collaborations between the public and private
494 sector. Furthermore, whilst some countries have a strongly centralised system (e.g. NL, SE, UK),
495 others are strongly decentralised (e.g. DE, ES, FR). Regional variability is more pronounced in
496 decentralised countries, which is difficult to capture. Lastly, some countries were concerned about
497 confidentiality, so that participation was only agreed on if data were presented in aggregated form
498 and countries were anonymised. These challenges were reflected by a wide range in the number of

499 reported components and percentage of obligatory EU components covered in the countries'
500 datasets. This latter percentage is underestimated as it is sometimes affected by the way
501 components were split (i.e. a country merging components not merged by other countries).
502 However, completeness has affected data quality in some countries, so that results have to be
503 interpreted with care and no between-country comparisons were attempted.

504 Another major limitation related to differences in applying terminology to specific components,
505 which led to initial high variability in how variables were categorized between countries. As a result,
506 extensive consistency checks were carried out and a terminology working group established to
507 improve the comparability of data. These inconsistencies in applying terminology and general
508 inconsistencies between data collected, as shown in this study, could therefore be used as a basis to
509 argue for a standardised documentation of the design of surveillance activities within the EU.
510 Documentation guidelines or standard forms have for example been developed by EFSA for
511 surveillance of *Echinococcus multilocularis* [50] and by the EU reference laboratory for surveillance of
512 fish diseases (http://www.eurl-fish.eu/Activities/survey_and_diagnosis.aspx). But no standard
513 requirements have been agreed on, which provide sufficient information to create an informed
514 overview, but sufficient flexibility to accommodate different approaches and preserve the necessary
515 degree of confidentiality.

516 *Recommendations regarding surveillance design*

517 It is difficult to make general recommendations regarding surveillance design as it depends on many
518 factors such as the hazard and population under surveillance, the hazard situation and objective.
519 When judging surveillance design, it is important to consider the surveillance system as a whole
520 including its passive and active components as components may complement each other. This
521 systems approach allows a) identifying surveillance gaps (i.e. sectors or age groups not covered) and
522 components with sub-optimal effectiveness and b) assessing opportunities to increase effectiveness
523 and economic efficiency.

524 The effectiveness of surveillance approaches can only be optimised if various surveillance designs are
525 formally compared as demonstrated manifold in published literature over recent years. This may
526 include comparisons of different testing regimes, sampling points and risk factors, strategies to
527 enhance awareness or incorporation of historical data. Hence, systematic documentation of current
528 designs, evaluation and comparisons with alternative strategies provide opportunities to select more
529 effective and efficient surveillance approaches. However, improved transparency and documentation
530 of design details may be needed to allow applying more flexible approaches.

531 *Recommendations derived from the process of collecting the data*

532 If registration of surveillance activities at country level was centralised, this would provide an
533 overview and allow for better coordination of efforts to be made between the public and private
534 sector. Furthermore, a minimum set of design variables could be defined in advance in order to
535 achieve consistency in documentation. This could be achieved through the use of the surveillance
536 design framework developed by the RISKSUR project, which provides a tool that can be used for
537 standardised documentation of surveillance efforts (<http://webtools.fp7-risksur.eu/>). Also, despite a
538 common source of definitions, terminology may lead to differences in interpretations when applied
539 to specific components, as shown by this study. Therefore, illustrating the correct application of
540 terminology based on specific components may be useful to supplement definitions and thus achieve
541 better consistency (<http://www.fp7-risksur.eu/terminology>). Given that surveillance can be
542 perceived to be a sensitive topic, it is also important to clearly explain to contributing parties the
543 purpose and expected outcome of more transparent documentation. Confidentiality concerns may
544 limit the application of alternative strategies, as these require transparent documentation to assess
545 the adequacy of assumptions and design specifications. However, these limitations stand in contrast
546 to the claim that surveillance is a public good [51]. Hence, there is a joint responsibility to address
547 factors limiting transparent documentation of surveillance activities.

548 All these aspects do not just pertain to this study but may cause problems with any compilation of
549 surveillance activities across EU Member States (e.g. EFSA reports, EU summary reports). Hence,
550 these gaps hinder information sharing in general and limit the ability to integrate information from
551 various sources (e.g. active/passive, public/private, different species) in a meaningful manner. It is
552 hypothesised that increased transparency would benefit all parties by enhancing trust, facilitating
553 meaningful comparisons, and allowing more targeted complementation of activities based on the
554 evaluation of the entire surveillance system rather than its individual components in isolation.

555 *Conclusions*

556 The study identified several gaps (lack of systematic documentation, inconsistent application of
557 terminology, little evidence of surveillance in species with low economic importance) and
558 opportunities (e.g. better uptake of alternative methods, increased use of stratified risk-based
559 sampling, application of novel approaches promoted as part of One Health). The greater flexibility
560 provided by the new EU Animal Health Law means that systematic evaluation of surveillance
561 alternatives will be required to ensure that surveillance is as efficient and effective as possible [52].

562 **SUPPLEMENTARY MATERIAL**

563 For supplementary material accompanying this paper visit XXX.

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575 CONFLICT OF INTEREST

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745 **TABLES**

746 **Table 1. Percentage of active surveillance components (number of recorded components / total**
 747 **number of recorded components) and 95% confidence intervals (95% CI) by surveillance design**
 748 **variables for all ten study countries and stratified by whether countries were partners of the EU-FP7**
 749 **RISKSUR project or not. Components comprised active surveillance components implemented in**
 750 **2011. Categories, for which confidence intervals between partner and non-partner countries did not**
 751 **overlap, are highlighted in grey.**

Variable (n) ^a	Category	All (n = 664)	Partner (n = 421)	Non-partner (n = 243)
Species (664 / 421 / 243)	Cattle	26.7 (23.3, 30.2)	26.8 (22.7, 31.3)	26.3 (20.9, 32.3)
	Pigs	17.5 (14.7, 20.6)	17.8 (14.3, 21.8)	16.9 (12.4, 22.2)
	Poultry	16.0 (13.3, 19.0)	14.0 (10.8, 17.7)	19.3 (14.6, 24.9)
	Small ruminants	11.9 (9.5, 14.6)	11.9 (8.9, 15.4)	11.9 (8.1, 16.7)
	Wildlife	10.2 (8.0, 12.8)	11.4 (8.5, 14.8)	8.2 (5.1, 12.4)
	<i>Equidae</i>	6.9 (5.1, 9.1)	7.4 (5.1, 10.3)	6.2 (3.5, 10.0)
	Multi	5.4 (3.8, 7.4)	5.0 (3.1, 7.5)	6.2 (3.5, 10.0)
	Other	5.4 (3.8, 7.4)	5.7 (3.7, 8.4)	4.9 (2.6, 8.5)
Management (615 / 418 / 197)	Public	65.4 (61.5, 69.1)	64.4 (59.6, 68.9)	67.5 (60.5, 74.0)
	Private	24.7 (21.4, 28.3)	23.2 (19.2, 27.6)	27.9 (21.8, 34.7)
	Both	9.9 (7.7, 12.6)	12.4 (9.4, 16.0)	4.6 (2.1, 8.5)
Area (662 / 421 / 241)	National	89.4 (86.8, 91.7)	87.4 (83.9, 90.4)	92.9 (88.9, 95.8)
	Regional	8.6 (6.6, 11.0)	9.7 (7.1, 13.0)	6.6 (3.8, 10.6)
	Local	2.0 (1.0, 3.3)	2.9 (1.5, 4.9)	0.4 (0, 2.3)
Obligation (645 / 417 / 228)	EU	68.4 (64.6, 71.9)	58.5 (53.6, 63.3)	86.4 (81.3, 90.6)
	National	11.6 (9.3, 14.4)	12.7 (9.7, 16.3)	9.6 (6.1, 14.2)
	Regional	2.2 (1.2, 3.6)	2.6 (1.3, 4.7)	1.3 (0.3, 3.8)
	Private	7.9 (5.9, 13)	11.8 (8.8, 15.2)	0.9 (0.1, 3.1)

Variable (n) ^a	Category	All (n = 664)	Partner (n = 421)	Non-partner (n = 243)
	None	9.9 (77, 125)	14.4 (11.2, 18.1)	1.8 (0.5, 4.4)
Objective (656 / 417 / 239)	Disease freedom	43.8 (399, 476)	41.7 (36.9, 46.6)	47.3 (40.8, 53.8)
	Case detection	26.8 (23.5, 30.4)	26.9 (22.7, 31.4)	26.8 (21.3, 32.9)
	Prevalence estimation	19.7 (16.7, 22.9)	22.5 (18.6, 26.9)	14.6 (10.4, 19.8)
	Early detection	9.8 (7.6, 12.3)	8.9 (6.3, 12.0)	11.3 (7.6, 16.0)
Sampling point (646 / 405 / 241)	Farm	48.6 (44.7, 52.5)	47.2 (42.2, 52.2)	51.0 (44.5, 57.5)
	Abattoir	21.4 (18.3, 24.7)	23.0 (19.0, 27.4)	18.7 (14.0, 24.2)
	Insemination	15.6 (12.9, 18.7)	14.8 (11.5, 18.7)	17.0 (12.5, 22.4)
	Wild	8.5 (6.5, 10.9)	8.4 (5.9, 11.5)	8.7 (5.5, 13.0)
	Rendering	3.7 (2.4, 5.5)	4.0 (2.3, 6.3)	3.3 (1.4, 6.4)
	Other	2.2 (1.2, 3.6)	2.7 (1.4, 4.8)	1.2 (0.3, 3.6)
Study type (655 / 415 / 240)	Continuous	56.8 (52.9, 60.6)	59.0 (54.1, 63.8)	52.9 (46.4, 59.4)
	Survey	39.2 (35.5, 43.1)	35.9 (31.3, 40.7)	45.0 (38.6, 51.5)
	Other	4.0 (2.6, 5.8)	5.1 (3.2, 7.6)	2.1 (0.7, 4.8)
Case definition (655 / 417 / 238)	Lab: Pathogen / toxin	42.9 (39.1, 46.8)	45.3 (40.5, 50.2)	38.7 (32.4, 45.2)
	Lab: Host response	37.9 (34.1, 41.7)	34.8 (30.2, 39.6)	43.3 (36.9, 49.8)
	Both	7.6 (5.7, 9.9)	5.5 (3.5, 8.2)	11.3 (7.6, 16.1)
	Clinical / pathological	2.9 (1.8, 4.5)	3.8 (2.2, 6.2)	1.3 (0.3, 3.6)
	Other	8.7 (6.7, 11.1)	10.6 (7.8, 13.9)	5.5 (2.9, 9.2)
Risk-based (641 / 413 / 228)	Yes	57.1 (53.2, 61.0)	52.1 (47.1, 57.0)	66.2 (59.7, 72.3)
	No	42.9 (39.0, 46.8)	47.9 (43.0, 52.9)	33.8 (27.7, 40.3)
Multi-hazard (579 / 396 / 183)	Yes	37.3 (33.4, 41.4)	40.4 (35.5, 45.4)	30.6 (24.0, 37.8)
	No	62.7 (58.6, 66.6)	59.6 (54.6, 64.5)	69.4 (62.2, 76.0)

752 ^a Number of observations for those categories listed for the respective variable. The difference in observations
753 compared to the number provided below the heading of 3rd to 5th column comprises the number of missing
754 observations per category.

755

756 Table 2. Column percentages and adjusted residuals (in brackets)^a of *management* versus variables for
 757 active surveillance components in 2011 recorded by 10 study countries included in the study (n = 615).

Variable	Category	Public	Private	Both
Partner country (n = 615)	Yes	66.9 (-0.77)	63.8 (-1.26)	85.3 (3.05)
	No	33.1 (0.77)	36.2 (1.26)	14.8 (-3.05)
Species group (n = 441)	Cattle	34.0 (-2.43)	46.6 (2.25)	42.2 (0.53)
	Pigs	23.8 (0.39)	22.9 (-0.07)	20.0 (-0.53)
	Poultry	20.8 (-0.35)	22.1 (0.27)	22.2 (0.16)
	Small ruminants	21.5 (3.09)	8.4 (-3.13)	15.6 (-0.27)
Geographical focus (n = 595)	National	89.3 (-3.27)	97.2 (2.70)	96.5 (1.33)
	Regional	10.7 (3.27)	2.8 (-2.70)	3.5 (-1.33)
Obligation (n = 610)	EU	72.3 (2.85)	65.8 (-0.79)	49.2 (-3.40)
	National or regional	16.4 (2.37)	5.9 (-3.29)	18.0 (0.97)
	Private or voluntary	11.3 (-5.63)	28.3 (3.95)	32.8 (3.25)
Surveillance objective (n = 608)	Disease freedom	39.9 (-3.00)	59.9 (4.48)	32.7 (-1.80)
	Case detection	25.9 (-1.05)	28.3 (0.32)	34.6 (1.26)
	Prevalence estimation	22.7 (3.00)	8.6 (-3.86)	23.6 (0.87)
	Early detection	11.5 (2.68)	3.3 (-2.92)	9.1 (-0.03)
Sampling point (n = 535)	Farm	58.0 (1.48)	43.8 (-3.32)	70.0 (2.40)
	Abattoir	30.5 (5.27)	8.3 (-4.89)	16.7 (-1.24)
	Rendering plant	5.1 (1.52)	0.0 (-2.91)	8.3 (1.75)
	Insemination centre	6.3 (-8.58)	47.9 (11.31)	5.0 (-2.69)
Study design (n = 609)	Continuous	61.2 (4.42)	39.5 (-4.35)	50.0 (-0.75)
	Survey	33.6 (-5.16)	58.6 (5.06)	46.6 (0.90)
	Other	5.3 (1.67)	2.0 (-1.62)	3.5 (-0.33)
Case definition (n = 556)	Direct	66.1 (2.77)	37.4 (-3.04)	50.1 (1.01)
	Serological	23.2 (-2.64)	54.7 (4.21)	36.3 (-2.15)
	Both	7.1 (-0.42)	3.6 (-2.44)	10.8 (2.48)

	Clinical / pathological	3.6 (0.15)	4.3 (0.83)	2.8 (-0.85)
Risk-based	Yes	53.1 (-2.42)	66.0 (2.66)	56.7 (0.00)
(n = 600)	No	46.9 (2.42)	34.0 (-2.66)	43.3 (0.00)
Multi-hazard	Yes	28.6 (-6.58)	68.1 (8.15)	31.7 (-1.21)
(n = 548)	No	71.4 (6.58)	31.9 (-8.15)	68.3 (1.21)

758 ^a Adjusted residuals greater than ± 1.96 were highlighted in bold as they are more extreme than what would be

759 expected if the null hypothesis of independence was true.

760

761 Table 3. Column percentages and adjusted residuals (in brackets)^a of livestock *species* versus variables
 762 for active surveillance components in 2011 recorded by 10 study countries (n = 487).

Variable	Category	Cattle	Pigs	Poultry	Small ruminants
Partner country (n = 487)	Yes	64.5 (0.75)	64.7 (0.57)	55.7 (-1.63)	63.3 (0.17)
	No	35.5 (-0.75)	35.3 (-0.57)	44.3 (1.63)	36.7 (-0.17)
Geographical focus (n = 474)	National	92.9 (-0.12)	89.0 (-1.89)	100.0 (3.20)	89.6 (-1.29)
	Regional	7.1 (0.12)	11.0 (1.89)	0.0 (-3.20)	10.4 (1.29)
Obligation (n = 472)	EU	68.1 (-0.51)	59.3 (-2.70)	86.7 (4.17)	65.8 (-0.78)
	National or regional	11.5 (-0.92)	23.0 (3.46)	6.1 (-2.36)	12.7 (-0.20)
	Private or voluntary	20.3 (1.45)	17.7 (0.17)	7.1 (-2.96)	21.5 (1.13)
Surveillance objective (n = 487)	Disease freedom	59.1 (4.36)	58.6 (2.97)	15.1 (-7.35)	41.8 (-0.94)
	Case detection	14.5 (-4.71)	17.2 (-2.59)	65.1 (10.18)	16.5 (-2.21)
	Prevalence estimation	21.0 (0.83)	14.7 (-1.39)	8.5 (-3.14)	35.4 (4.04)
	Early detection	5.4 (-1.57)	9.5 (0.77)	11.3 (1.53)	6.3 (-0.53)
Sampling point (n = 456)	Farm	46.0 (-3.07)	37.2 (-4.40)	89.1 (7.36)	61.3 (1.20)
	Abattoir	20.5 (-0.60)	38.1 (4.78)	10.9 (-2.87)	14.7 (-1.66)
	Rendering plant	6.3 (1.33)	0.9 (-2.18)	0.0 (-2.36)	12.0 (3.34)
	Insemination centre	27.3 (3.87)	23.9 (1.73)	0.0 (-5.10)	12.0 (-1.57)
Study design (n = 481)	Continuous	51.6 (-0.55)	55.7 (0.60)	60.4 (1.67)	43.4 (-1.87)
	Survey	44.6 (0.24)	41.7 (-0.53)	37.7 (-1.44)	54.0 (1.93)
	Other	3.8 (0.92)	2.6 (-0.22)	1.9 (-0.71)	2.6 (-0.16)
Case definition (n = 452)	Direct	36.0 (-2.20)	24.6 (-4.48)	71.8 (6.75)	44.9 (0.38)
	Serological	55.3 (2.30)	60.9 (3.11)	24.3 (-5.49)	46.2 (-0.36)
	Both	7.5 (0.67)	10.0 (1.76)	1.9 (-2.11)	5.1 (-0.51)
	Clinical / pathological	1.2 (-1.39)	4.6 (1.42)	1.9 (-0.51)	3.9 (0.72)
Risk-based	Yes	65.6 (1.23)	50.4 (-2.95)	62.3 (0.05)	71.1 (1.76)

(n = 477)	No	34.4 (-1.23)	49.6 (2.95)	37.7 (-0.05)	29.0 (-1.76)
Multi-hazard	Yes	44.0 (2.61)	59.0 (5.44)	8.1 (-6.64)	25.0 (-2.09)
(n = 426)	No	56.0 (-2.61)	41.0 (-5.44)	91.9 (6.64)	75.0 (2.09)

763 ^a Adjusted residuals greater than ± 1.96 were highlighted in bold as they are more extreme than what would be

764 expected if the null hypothesis of independence was true.

765

766 Table 4. Column percentages and adjusted residuals (in brackets)^a of *surveillance objective* versus
 767 variables for active surveillance components in 2011 recorded by 10 study countries (n = 656).

Variable	Category	Case detection	Early detection	Disease freedom	Prevalence estimation
Partner country (n = 656)	Yes	63.6 (0.02)	57.8 (-1.01)	60.6 (-1.38)	72.9 (2.45)
	No	36.4 (-0.02)	42.2 (1.01)	39.4 (1.38)	27.1 (-2.45)
Geographical focus (n = 636)	National	91.2 (-0.36)	84.4 (-2.29)	95.7 (3.11)	88.0 (-1.74)
	Regional	8.8 (0.36)	15.6 (2.29)	4.3 (-3.11)	12.0 (1.74)
Obligation (n = 636)	EU	65.5 (-0.96)	45.5 (-3.83)	76.4 (3.86)	64.6 (-1.04)
	National or regional	13.2 (-0.21)	23.6 (2.25)	11.4 (-1.47)	15.0 (0.47)
	Private or voluntary	21.3 (1.35)	30.9 (2.63)	12.1 (-3.37)	20.5 (0.84)
Sampling point (n = 574)	Farm	79.4 (7.28)	71.7 (2.37)	40.4 (-6.31)	46.9 (-1.94)
	Abattoir	19.4 (-1.40)	23.9 (0.10)	19.2 (-2.09)	38.1 (4.12)
	Rendering plant	1.3 (-2.18)	4.4 (0.06)	1.2 (-3.22)	15.0 (6.44)
	Insemination centre	0.0 (-6.84)	0.0 (-3.25)	39.2 (12.31)	0.0 (-5.45)
Study design (n = 649)	Continuous	69.9 (4.01)	73.4 (2.80)	36.3 (-9.42)	77.3 (5.19)
	Survey	28.3 (-3.36)	0.0 (-6.74)	62.7 (10.92)	20.3 (-4.83)
	Other	1.7 (-1.78)	26.6 (9.69)	1.1 (-3.38)	2.3 (-1.07)
Case definition (n = 592)	Direct	68.6 (6.36)	24.0 (-3.38)	27.6 (-8.64)	72.8 (6.20)
	Serological	24.4 (-5.17)	44.0 (0.32)	60.7 (8.53)	20.2 (-5.23)
	Both	4.5 (-1.93)	20.0 (3.22)	10.3 (1.80)	2.6 (-2.38)
	Clinical / pathological	2.6 (-0.53)	12.0 (3.69)	1.5 (-2.21)	4.4 (0.79)
Risk-based	Yes	57.9 (0.37)	50.0 (-1.14)	63.3 (2.97)	44.2 (-3.21)

(n = 635)	No	42.1 (-0.37)	50.0 (1.14)	36.7 (-2.97)	55.8 (3.21)
Multi-hazard	Yes	18.7 (-5.37)	35.1 (-0.22)	59.5 (9.83)	12.8 (-5.95)
(n = 571)	No	81.3 (5.37)	64.9 (0.22)	40.5 (-9.83)	87.2 (5.95)

768 ^a Adjusted residuals greater than ± 1.96 were highlighted in bold as they are more extreme than what would be

769 expected if the null hypothesis of independence was true.

770

771 Table 5. Percentage of risk-based sampling components (n = 366) stratified by risk factor (95% CI: 95%
 772 confidence interval). Multiple selections of risk factors per components were allowed. The risk-based
 773 components were a subset of active surveillance components (n = 664) recorded for 10 study countries
 774 for the year 2011.

Risk factor	Percentage of components (95% CI)	Main type	Comments (remaining components either other type or unknown)
Production type	45.1% (39.9%, 53%)	Targeted	142/165: Only breeding animals; 96/142: Surveillance in artificial insemination centres
Age	24.3% (2%, 29.0%)	Targeted	36/89: Serological components targeting only older animals; 37/89: BSE/scrapie components targeting older animals only
Region	13.1% (9.8%, 17.0%)	Stratified	27/48: Surveillance intensity depended on epidemiological situation in the region
Herd size	11.2% (8.2%, 14.9%)	Targeted	37/41: Only large sized farms were targeted
Time period	6.0% (3.8%, 9.0%)	Varies	Restricted to high-risk period (e.g. demonstrate freedom at end of high-risk period) or different sampling intensity between seasons
Production for human consumption	3.6% (1.9%, 6.0%)	Targeted	
Farm factors	3.8% (2.1%, 6.3%)	Varies	5/13: Targeting only outdoor farms
Species	2.5% (1.1%, 4.6%)	Varies	Since components were generally split by species, this risk factor was predominantly recorded for avian influenza (distinction between wild bird and waterfowl species)
Event	2.2% (9%, 4.3%)	Targeted	Testing prior to transport

Disease status of the herd	2.2% (9%, 4.3%)	Targeted	E.g. certified free herds versus non-free herds
Trade	1.1% (3%, 2.8%)	Varies	Trade volume (e.g. out-degree movements)
Previous	2.2% (9%, 4.3%)	Stratified	Previous irregularities or positive findings
Various	8% (2%, 2.4%)	NA ^a	
Unknown	1.9% (8%, 3.9%)	NA ^a	

775

^a Not applicable.